

CHEMISTRY SCIENCES

SOME PECULIARITIES OF THE USE OF POLYPHOSPHAZENES AS ANTIPYRENES IN POLYETHYLENE COMPOSITIONS

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Abstract

Some peculiarities of the use of oligo-polyphosphazenes as antipyrenes in polymer-polymer mixtures on the basis of HPPE with different phosphazene content (to 6%) have been considered. The physical-chemical, deformation-strength and tribological properties of compositions depending on their composition have been studied. The results clearly indicate the expediency of the use of hexachlorocyclotriphosphazene in the compositions on the basis of polyethylene.

Keywords: polyethylene, composition, polyphosphazene, antipyrene.

Introduction

In polymer materials science, an actual problem is the reduction of the combustibility of the industrial polymers. The consumers of polymer materials hardly-inflammable and not supporting combustion are the industry of all types of transport, construction, electrical industry, up to household products [1-3]. The problem is that the combustion of the polymer materials is accompanied by the isolation of a large quantity of smoke and toxic products. The situation is aggravated by the fact that some additives introduced into the polymer composition, sometimes in sufficiently large quantities, as in a case with plasticizers, as a rule increase the inflammability of the polymer materials [4,5].

The effective inhibitors of combustion processes of the polymer are phosphorus and nitrogen-containing compounds [6]. Among such compounds, the oligomer and polymer organophosphazenes synthesized by the substitution of the chlorine atoms in hexachlorocyclotriphosphazene (HCCPh) or polydichlorophosphazene (PDCPh) deserve attention. Moreover, an essential index determining fire resistance is the concentration of phosphorus atoms in a molecule of phosphazene compound. In this case, the polyphosphazenes of cyclic structure have an advantage over linear ones due to the

effect of the end groups [7]. As a consequence, at the same content, the compositions with cyclic additives are more fire-resistant. However, it has been shown using the example of the chlorinated polyethylene that in the absence of the halogen atoms in phosphorus-containing antipyrene, the essential decrease in flammability and self-extinguishing is not observed [8].

There are numerous publications in the literature on the use of halogen-containing and substituted organophosphazenes in a wide range of fire-resistant, low-smoke compositions and plasticizers [9-13]. However, most of them are patent publications. Naturally, the role of the used additives is not limited only with the demonstration of the antipyretic properties. As a rule, the complex changes in the physical-chemical and mechanical properties of the obtained compositions are observed to one degree or another [24,25].

The purpose of this work was the comparative study of the behavior of hexachlorocyclotriphosphazene and linear polydichlorophosphazene as an active additive to high-pressure polyethylene. In this case, the main attention was paid to elucidation of the influence of these additives on the peculiarities of changes in the physical-chemical and mechanical properties of the obtained compositions.

Experimental part

Hexachlorocyclotriphosphazene was obtained by the interaction of phosphorus pentachloride with ammonium chloride in chlorobenzene according to the methods given in work [14]. Polydichlorophosphazene was synthesized by the thermal polymerization of hexachlorocyclotriphosphazene in a melt according to the method [15], due to the recommendation of work [16]. In the work, HPPE of mark 15802-020 with a density of 915kg/m^3 , a melt flow index of $1,98\text{g}/10\text{min}$ and a degree of crystallinity $\sim 48\%$ were used.

The compositions of polyethylene with trimmer and quantity of components with polydichlorophosphazene were obtained by mixing a certain quantity of components in a single-screw extruder with screw diameter of $0,03\text{ m}$, screw length – $0,30\text{ l}$, screw rotation rate– $60\text{ rev}/\text{min}$, at temperature $433\text{-}438^\circ\text{K}$ on the cylinder zone. The obtained compositions were granulated and after conditioning, the sheets with a thickness of $0,002\text{ m}$ were pressed from them at 433°K and pressure of 10MPa . The samples were cut from the molded sheets for carrying out the necessary measurements and tests in accordance with the requirements of the corresponding standards.

The determination of the abrasive wear of the samples was carried out according to GOST 11012-69. The method of investigation has been based on the wear of the samples on sumbat polishing paper. The essence of the method consists in determination of the reduction in the volume of the sample as a result of friction. The sample dimensions are as follows: $10\times 10\times 10\text{-}20\text{ mm}$ [23].

Results and discussion

It is clear from the patent materials that in polyethylene compositions for providing antipyretic properties, the content of organophosphazenes is usually 8-

10% [17]. In a case of the use of halophosphazenes for giving self-extinguishing to the compositions, taking into account the relatively high content of the phosphorus and chlorine atoms (more than 26 and 61%, respectively), the maximum quantity of antipyrenes in the compositions can be 4-6% (mass). The higher hydrolytic stability of the cyclic hexachlorocyclotriphosphazene (HCCPh) in comparison with tetra-octa- and polydichlorophosphazenes (PDCPh) [18,19], along with some advantage on elemental composition [7,20-22], makes more advisable the use of the cyclic HCCPh in polymer-oligomer and polymer-polymer compositions. However, the final selection between HCCPh and PDCPh can be made from the results of the comparative study of the physical-chemical and mechanical properties of PE/HCCPh and PE/PDCPh mixtures with various phosphazene content in the composition. We have prepared the polymer-polymer mixtures on the basis of HPPE and HCCPh (PDCPh) with content of the latter one up to 6% and studied their properties

Some physical-chemical and deformation-strength parameters of the studied HPPE/HCCPh compositions are shown in Fig. 1 and 2 as the concentration dependencies. As can be seen from Fig.1., with an increase in the HCCPh content in the composition, a monotonous increase in the density and melt flow index of the compositions is observed. Based on the experimental density values, the degree of crystallinity of HPPE-matrix for each composition has been calculated using an additive scheme. In the concentration range of 0-6% mass, there is a slight decrease in the degree of crystallinity of PE, especially noticeable in the initial section of the graph (up to 2%). Apparently, this has been connected with certain, although limited compatibility of HPPE with HCCPh. In a low content (1-2%) of the latter one, the presence of HPPE in HCCPh matrix somewhat hinders the crystallization process.

Fig.1. Dependence of physical-chemical indices on the composition of HPPE compositions with cyclic trimmer of HCCPh.

- - degree of crystallinity of HPPE – matrix,
- melt flow density,
- - melt flow index

In accordance with the above-mentioned one, with an increase of HCCPh content in the composition, the change in the tensile deformation-strength properties is observed (Fig.2). The deep minimum on the graph, in the field of low concentrations, has been apparently

connected with the presence of the amorphous and crystalline phases of HPPE–HCCPh. However, in an increase of HCCPh content in the interphase fields, it is observed the practically complete establishment of physical-mechanical parameters to the initial values.

Fig.2. Dependence of physical-mechanical indices on the composition of HPPE compositions with cyclic trimmer of HCCPh.

- - tensile strength,
- breaking deformation,
- - tensile yield strength.

Other picture is observed in the physical-chemical and mechanical properties of the composition of HPPE with PDCPh (Fig.3.) In this case, the presence of PDCPh in HPPE- matrix up to 5% content has little effect on the strength of the composition, although a

slight increase in melt flow is observed. However, the deformation properties of the compositions are sharply decreased up to brittle fracture with 5% content of PDCPh in the composition.

Fig.3. Dependence of some indices on the composition of HPPE compositions with PDCPh.

- - tensile strength,
- melt flow index,
- - breaking deformation

In Table, the results of the investigation of the tribological properties of filled hexachlorocyclotriphosphazene of high-pressure polyethylene are presented. In this case, the samples of filled HCCPh (1-6% mass) were used. It was important to find out how the influence of quantity on the wear resistance of the polymer composite would be most affected. Analyzing the data presented in this table, it can be seen that the introduction of even 1.0% of the mass of HCCPh leads to an essential increase in the wear resistance of the polymer. As a rule, the surface of the active filler particles has a sufficiently high adsorption capacity, as a result of

which the macro-chain segments are fixed on it. In this case, the orientation of macro-segments on the surface of the particles occurs with the formation of a monolayer. It is possible that on the surface of the first monolayer, but to a lesser extent, the orientation of macro-segments also occurs. The orientation processes will weaken in the direction of the volume of the polymer matrix. Based on this, it can be assumed that with increase of the adhesive interaction in the polymer-filler system, the thickness of the formed interphase layer is also increased.

Table.

Influence of concentration of hexachlorocyclotriphosphazene on wear resistance of composites on the basis of HPPE.

№	Composition of polymer composite (HPPE +% mass. HCCPh)	Wear in the first cycle, mg
1	HPPE	147.12
2	HPPE +1.0HCCPh	57.25
3	HPPE +2.0HCCPh	41.37
4	HPPE +3.0HCCPh	37.15
5	HPPE +4.0HCCPh	33.59
6	HPPE +5.0HCCPh	39.18
7	HPPE +6.0HCCPh	65.53

Thus, the obtained results clearly indicate the preference for the use of HCCPh in fire-resistant and self-extinguishing compositions on the basis of polyethylene.

References

- Berlin A.I. On the fundamental concepts of chemistry // *Soros Educational Journal*. 1996, no. 9, pp. 57.
- Volkov V.P., Zelenetsky A.N., Sizova M.D., Zelenetsky S.N., et al. Polyethylene compositions with reduced combustibility // *Plastic masses*. 2007, no. 2, pp. 7-13.
- Kopylov V.V., Novikov S.N., Oxentievich P.A. Polymer materials with reduced combustibility (ed. by A.N. Pravodnikov). Moscow: Khimiya. 1986. p. 8-18.
- Vindizheva A.S., Sapaev Kh.Kh., Moussov I.V., Khatirova S.Yu., Likhedov M.H., Mikitaev A.K. Development of fire-resistant polyvinyl chloride plasticate // *Plastic masses*. 2011, no. 10, pp. 34-36.
- Pat. US 6448310B1 (publ. 2002). Flame retardant composition.
- Volkov V.P., Zelenetsky A.N., Sizova M.D., Rudakova T.A., Zelenetsky S.N., Shevchenko V.G., Obolonkova E.S., Kerekyan A.S., Egorova N.A. Principles of preparation of polyethylene compositions with reduced combustibility and special properties // *Plastic masses*. 2006, no. 7, pp. 12-19.
- Pat. US 7060744 (publ. 2006). Phosphazene composition.
- Schroeder J.P., Sopchak W.P. The reaction of phosphorus trichloride and oxygen with polymers // *Journal of Polymer Science*. 1960, vol. 47, no. 149, pp. 417-433.
- Pat. US 4042561A (publ. 1977). Flame retardant compositions containing polyphosphazenes.
- Pat. US 4083820A (publ. 1978). Low smoke polyphosphazene compositions.
- Pat. US 4107108A (publ. 1978). Polyphosphazene plasticized resins.
- Pat. US 5639808A (publ. 1997). Flame retardant thermosettable resin compositions.
- Pat. US 6518336B1 (publ. 2003). Flame-retardant resin compositions comparing thermoplastic resin, thermotropic liquid crystal polymer, and halogen-free phosphazene compound.
- Buravov B.A., Bochkarev E.S., Al-Khamzawi A., Tuzhikov O.O., Tuzhikov O.I. Modern tendencies in the development of flame retardants for polymer compositions. Composition, properties, application // *Proceedings of the Volgograd State Technical University*. 2020, no. 12(247), pp. 7-24.
- Afanasyev S.V., Balakin V.M. Flame retardants based on phosphorus-containing compounds and aminoaldehyde resins // *Proceedings of Samara Scientific Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences*. 2014, vol. 16, no. 1(16), pp. 1682-1684.
- Sirotnin I.S., Bilichenko Yu.V., Suraeva O.V., Solodukhin A.N., Kireev A.V. Synthesis of oligomeric chlorophosphazenes in the presence of ZnCl₂ // *Polymer science*. 2013, vol. 55B, no. 2, pp. 218-224. DOI: 10.7868/80507547513020116.
- Olcock G.H. Phosphor-nitrogenous compounds. M.: MirMir. 1976. 536 p.
- Tour D.R., Korshak V.V., Vinogradova S.V., Pavlova S.A., Timofeeva G.I., Gogvadze Ts.A., Alikhanov N.O. // *DAN USSR*. 1986. 291. C364-367.
- Pat. JP111263885 Япония.
- Trinquier F. Structure, stability, and bonding in cyclodiphosphazene and cyclotriphosphazene // *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 1986, vol. 108, no. 4, pp. 568-577. DOI: 10.1021/ja00264a002

21. Davydova V.I., Voronkov M.G. Polyphosphazenes. Moscow-Leningrad: Publishing House of the Academy of Sciences. 1962. 87 p.

22. G.Ş. Qasımova, N.T. Qəhrəmanov., Yüksək-mexanikivətriboloji xassələrməlik polimerkompozit materiallar, Azər poliqrafiya, 1922.

23. N.T. Kakhramanov, G.Sh. Gasimova, S.S. Psetskiy, J.N. Kakhramanly, Physical and mechanical properties of nanocomposites based on block copolymer propylene with ethylene and graphite Chemical Problems. 2019. No. 1. P. 72-80

24. Arzumanova N.B., Kakhramanov N.T., Mammadli U.M., Lalayeva R.N., Guliyev A.M. Physical-mechanical properties of nano-composites based on ethylene-propylene block copolymer. Chemical Problems. 2017. No. 2. P. 167-172

25. Gasimova, G.Sh. Problem state of obtaining and research of composite materials based on polyolefins and minerals // Processes of Petrochemistry and oil refining, – Baku: – 2020. vol. 21, №1, – p. 60-70.